

TITLE: **TEMPLATE-BASED MULTI-AGENT PLAN RECOGNITION FOR
TACTICAL SITUATION ASSESSMENT**

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Template-Based Multi-Agent Plan Recognition for Tactical Situation Assessment

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ABSTRACT

Under investigation is the concept of a multi-agent Plan Recognition Model to assist a Naval tactical decision maker in interpreting the activity of enemy ships and aircraft (agents) and predicting their goals and plans*. Multi-agent templates have been devised to capture the tactical decision maker's knowledge of how the plans of individual agents interact in pursuit of shared goals. The templates provide a flexible knowledge representation that allows the Plan Recognition Model to reason about different situation-specific variations in the ways multi-agent plans may unfold. Template instances form hypotheses of future agent actions and are created in a top-down/bottom-up manner. The hypotheses are then updated based on observations of agent behavior. The plan recognition process features mechanisms to curb the proliferation of hypotheses possible in multi-agent domains.

1. INTRODUCTION

Tactical decision makers in a Naval warfare environment must decide how to allocate their combat assets to respond to the activities of many potentially hostile platforms (e.g. aircraft and ships) threatening a Naval Battle Group. These platforms represent multiple agents operating either individually, or in combination, to carry out military operations in support of shared higher level goals ranging from monitoring to attacking the Battle Group. The decision maker's interpretation of the agents' behavior can be cast as a form of plan recognition. This premise asserts that the tactical observer interprets the activity of hostile agents by hypothesizing their goals and inferring the plans being carried out to achieve those goals. An on-line, automated plan recognition system would assist the decision maker in analyzing the data on agent activity to correctly anticipate and respond to hypothesized future actions. Feasibility of this concept is under investigation through the development of an experimental multi-agent plan recognition model (PRM).

Previous work in plan recognition has addressed problem domains such as everyday event and action perception [11], story understanding [12], discourse analysis [9], and intelligent user interfaces [6]. Attempts have been made to formulate a general theory [7]. However, these efforts have not focused on the complexities of multi-agent domains where the agents

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and observer are in an adversarial posture with respect to each other.

Our work has progressed from a single agent/multiple hypothesis model [2] to a multi-agent model with enhanced goal/plan hierarchies designed to capture the interaction among multiple adversarial agents under observation [3]. Further development and refinement of the knowledge representation, the creation of multi-agent hypotheses, and the plan recognition process is the focus of this paper.

2. PRM ARCHITECTURE AND KNOWLEDGE REPRESENTATION

The high-level design of the PRM forms an architecture of cognition derived from Anderson [1] (see Figure 1). In an interpretation of Anderson's work, human cognition can be partitioned into three components: long term memory, procedural memory, and short term memory. Using this model for plan recognition allows us to more readily partition, and reason with, the problem solving knowledge applied in the plan recognition process.

Figure 1 - Plan Recognition Model Architecture

Long Term Memory (LTM) contains the decision maker's knowledge of the goals and plans that adversarial agents pursue in certain tactical situations. Procedural Memory (PM) contains mechanisms that enable the PRM to reason about multi-agent activities. These include control structures, search strategies, pattern matching strategies, etc. PM accesses information about the agents and the tactical situation in the World Model (WM) to retrieve candidate goal/plan structures from LTM.

These are instantiated as hypotheses in Short Term Memory (STM) to predict future agent activity. PM then matches the observations of agent behavior against the hypotheses in STM and computes a degree of belief for each hypothesis. This degree of belief is derived from the degree of fit of hypothesis attributes to the WM data. WM is populated with facts and state variable information that is contained in data reports of agent behavior input to the system from external sources. Also present in WM is contextual information pertaining to the state of the world: the theater of operations, geographical and environmental features, political tensions, etc.

2.1 Long Term Memory

In our domain, multiple agents operate as instruments of a single, high-level "master" agent. Each of these agents pursue actions to fulfill subgoals in support of higher-level goals shared with the master agent. LTM consists of a goal/mission/plan hierarchy which contains structures which represent the knowledge about possible goals in the domain and known ways agents may interact to achieve those goals. The knowledge is partitioned into three levels: goals, multi-agent missions, and single-agent plans (see Figure 2).

Figure 2 - LTM Goal/Plan Hierarchy

Goal/Mission/Plan Hierarchy. Top-level nodes of the goal/mission/plan hierarchy are used to represent high-level goals of an agent. These nodes in turn represent states of WM which may potentially be desired by this master agent. Individual subordinate agents work together to pursue one or more subgoals that comprise necessary intermediate state changes in a progression toward the desired goal states. Based on postulated goals, the PRM need focus only on expected multi-agent behavior in pursuit of those goals, rather than all possible behavior. Goals are postulated top-down by assessing the shortfall between the desired goal states and the current state in WM. The state of the tactical situation represented in WM will dictate which of these goals will be desired by agents under observation.

Goals are achieved through **multi-agent missions** which are carried out through the interaction of multiple cooperating agents. The multi-agent missions are represented as templates in LTM which are general scripts with various required and optional components (i.e. single-agent plans).

The templates represent the various ways in which single-agent plans combine to carry out multi-agent missions. For example, in support of the DESTROY-TARGET goal, the multi-agent ATTACK mission has required plans consisting of the actual STRIKE itself, and optional plans including TANKING and FEINT. The ATTACK mission may also draw upon a plan from the MONITOR mission to satisfy the KNOW-TARGET-LOCATION state which is a precondition for the STRIKE plan.

Successful multi-agent missions to achieve a goal may differ according to circumstances in WM, such as the political climate, available platforms, spatial considerations, and weather conditions. These circumstances dictate the specific set of single-agent plans configured for an STM template instance (see Figure 3). In the ATTACK example, if a likely target is a sufficient distance from the attacking agents, the agents will require tanking (mid-air refueling) to execute the mission. Thus there should be expectation of the tanking plan in the context of this particular ATTACK mission. A template instance in STM will include the TANKING plan. There will be no expectation of the TANKING plan if the attacking agents are close enough to the target to enable unrefueled flight.

Figure 3 - Multi-Agent Template

The templates also capture permissible variations in the temporal sequence of their constituent single-agent plans (see Figure 4). Time intervals describing when the plan may be initiated and when the critical event of the plan may be performed are specified for each single-agent plan in a multi-agent template. The initiation interval specifies the range across time in which the performance of the plan may begin; the critical interval specifies the range across time in which the primary activity of the plan takes place.

Plans are the single-agent components of the multi-agent templates. Plans consist of sequences of actions carried out by a single agent to effect desired state changes necessary for the completion of a multi-agent mission. A plan has a Deterministic Finite Automata (DFA) representation of legal sequences of events that comprise that plan [2]. The plans reside in a plan library since a plan may be a component of several different missions. No plan is specific to any multi-agent mission template, but may be used by any multi-agent mission template requiring this component.

Figure 4 - Sample Multi-Agent Template Plan Temporal Sequence

Generic Node Representation. Each of the goals, missions, plans, and events are represented as nodes in the hierarchy. Each node is a frame-like representation consisting of three classes of attributes: conditional attributes, execution, and effects (see Figure 5).

Conditional attributes are a set of parameters whose (at least partial) satisfaction provides evidence for a particular hypothesized goal, mission, plan, or event. Each type of conditional attribute is described below.

Preconditions specify necessary conditions for the performance of a mission, plan, or event. Preconditions are used to reduce the search space when postulating goals, missions, plans, and events in a top-down fashion (see Section 3.1). Precondition satisfaction means that conditions are such that the agent could possibly perform the action described by the LTM node; it does not imply that the action is currently being performed. Functional dependencies between the single-agent plans within, and across, multi-agent templates are represented as preconditions in the individual plan structures. For example, the KNOW-TARGET-LOCATION state, achieved by a MONITOR-type plan, is a precondition for activation of an ATTACK mission hypothesis.

:NAME	SAMPLE-NODE
:TYPE	SAMPLE
:PRECONDITIONS	(AND (:IMPACT I-1 PRECONDITION-1) (:IMPACT I-2 PRECONDITION-2) (:IMPACT I-3 CONSTRAINT-1) (:IMPACT I-4 CONSTRAINT-2))
:CONSTRAINTS	(AND (:IMPACT I-5 EXPECTED-1) (OR (:IMPACT I-6 EXPECTED-2) (:IMPACT I-7 EXPECTED-3)))
:EXPECTED-CONDITIONS	(OR* (:IMPACT I-8 OBSERVABLE-1) (:IMPACT I-9 OBSERVABLE-2) (AND (:IMPACT I-10 OBSERVABLE-3) (:IMPACT I-11 OBSERVABLE-4)))
:OBSERVABLE-CONDITIONS	(OR* (:IMPACT I-12 CRITICAL-INDICATOR-1) (:IMPACT I-13 CRITICAL-INDICATOR-2))
:EXECUTION	(ACCOMPLISHED-BY (CHILD-NODE-A CHILD-NODE-B))
:EFFECTS	((EFFECT-1) (EFFECT-2) ... (EFFECT-N))

Figure 5 - Generic Node Representation

Constraints are those necessary conditions that must remain satisfied for the agent to perform actions described by the LTM node. The state of being "Within-Weapons-Launch-Range" is a constraint imposed on maintaining the on-station, or critical event of a STRIKE plan.

Expected conditions are those expected to be satisfied when an agent performs node-specified actions. Expected conditions facilitate the prediction component of the PRM: the degree to which the expected conditions match facts in WM allows us to predict the likelihood of an agent performing some action before any node-specific evidence is directly observable. For example, an expected condition for an ATTACK hypothesis is a state of "Heightened-Tensions" in WM; note that this is not a precondition for an ATTACK mission to be performed, nor is it directly observable.

Observable conditions are manifestations of an agent's behavior recorded when an agent is pursuing some action associated with an LTM node. Observable conditions provide for the recognition component of the PRM and are generally associated with the events of a given plan. Through the accumulation of observed evidence, we recognize that an agent is performing some action characteristic of an event in a plan. A "Weapons-Launch-Radar" emission is an observable manifestation of an agent in the on-station event of a STRIKE-type plan.

Critical Indicators are those observable conditions with sufficient discriminatory power to indicate that the agent is pursuing activity described by a particular LTM node. Critical indicators provide the means for bottom-up activation of hypotheses described in Section 3.1. They insure hypothesis activation in circumstances where evidence necessary for top-down activation through preconditions/expected condition satisfaction was insufficient. A report of a sighting of a "Weapons-Carrying-Attack-Aircraft" is an example of a critical indicator for an ATTACK.

Execution Attributes define child nodes of an LTM node. These consist of subordinate goals, missions, plans, and events invoked by the agent to pursue activity in support of the parent node. Child nodes define either: 1) the ways to accomplish the parent node (e.g. an ATTACK goal may be accomplished by one of several ATTACK-type missions, or 2) the way the parent node is executed (e.g. a STRIKE plan decomposes into the sequence of events necessary to execute a strike against a target).

Effects are similar to the Add and Delete lists found in STRIPS-like representations of actions. For example, an effect of a successful STRIKE will be a "Target-Destroyed" fact added to WM along with associated state variable updates.

Combination of Evidence within Conditional Attributes. In the tactical domain, much of the data describing the adversary's behavior is either missing or ambiguous. The discriminatory power of a piece of data and its likelihood of being obtained will effect the confidence level of a hypothesis which requires it. The data required by the conditional attributes associated with a hypothesis node are not considered equally in the decision making process. Each conditional attribute has an impact [5] which reflects the decision maker's opinion of the relative worth of this parameter in determining the overall belief in a hypothesis. The impact may range from -1.0, which signifies high negative evidence for a hypothesis given the match of the parameter, through 0.0, which signifies that the parameter supplies no evidence for or against the

hypothesis, through +1.0, which signifies that the parameter will contribute high positive evidence to the hypothesis.

The matches of the conditional attributes are combined through the use of :AND, :OR, and :OR* connectives (see Figure 5). The :AND stipulates that all of the conditions must be true, requiring at least a partial match for all conditions. This connective is used to specify necessary conditions (positive impact) for a node object. When combining the degree of match (DOM) for n conditions within the context of an :AND block, we use the following weighted average computation (equation 1).

$$DOM_{AND} = \frac{\sum_{i=1}^n \text{impact}_i (\text{dom}_i)}{\sum_{i=1}^n \text{ABS}(\text{impact}_i)} \quad (1)$$

A weighted average computation is used since each piece of information has a number of "votes" in the overall DOM reflected by both its impact and its calculated local DOM.

The :OR requires that only one of the conditions must be met; this connective allows us to express sufficient conditions. When calculating the local DOM within the context of the :OR, we only return the first match times its impact, disregarding any other conditions that may also match.

The :OR*, however, requires at least one of the conditions to be true, but does not disregard the rest of the satisfied conditions as in the :OR; it is therefore computationally more expensive. All of the satisfied conditions, with both positive and negative impact, are accumulated within the :OR*. When combining the degree of match for n conditionals within the context of an :OR* block we use a disjunctive evidence combination computation [5] that has been modified to handle negative impact parameters. If negative impact parameters are present, we must accumulate separately both evidence for and against a hypothesis (i.e. measure of belief (MB) and measure of disbelief (MD)). The MB (equation 2) and MD (equation 3) are calculated individually.

$$MB = 1 - \prod_{i=1}^m [1 - (\text{posimpact}_i \cdot \text{dom}_i)] \quad (2)$$

$$MD = 1 - \prod_{j=1}^n [1 - (\text{negimpact}_j \cdot \text{dom}_j)] \quad (3)$$

In computing the overall DOM (equation 4), the MB and MD are scaled with respect to the amount of positive and negative evidence which has been collected for the hypothesis.

$$DOM_{OR*} = \frac{MB \cdot (\sum_{i=1}^m \text{posimpact}_i) - MD \cdot (\sum_{j=1}^n \text{negimpact}_j)}{\text{MAX}(\sum_{i=1}^m \text{posimpact}_i, \sum_{j=1}^n \text{negimpact}_j)} \quad (4)$$

In the modified disjunctive DOM calculation, the more positive evidence available, the higher the DOM that can be expected, likewise, the more negative evidence, the lower the overall DOM.

If there are missing local parameter DOMs for the OR*, we exploit the fact that the match between a datum and the expected value of a conditional attribute must have one of three possible states: match (or partial match), no match, or indeterminate [10]. Since the three states of a match are mutually exclusive, we use the :OR connective to capture their effects on conditional attributes. For example, since we expect an ATTACK-type platform to be conducting a STRIKE-type plan, we represent the possible states of platform identification as follows:

$$\begin{aligned} (&OR \quad (:IMPACT \ 0.9 \ (PLATFORM-TYPE \ ATTACK)) \\ &\quad \quad (:IMPACT \ -0.6 \ (PLATFORM-TYPE \ NON-ATTACK)) \\ &\quad \quad (:IMPACT \ 0.5*PD \ (PLATFORM-TYPE \ UNKNOWN))) \end{aligned}$$

If we observe behavior of a platform known to be of an ATTACK-type, the high positive impact of this parameter supplies strong evidence for a STRIKE plan hypothesis. If we know that the platform is not an ATTACK-type, then the moderate-to-high negative impact supplies evidence against the hypothesis. Finally, if data regarding the platform type is missing, we multiply the "probability of datum" (PD) by the impact of data absence. For the above example, PD is the prior likelihood of the platform being an ATTACK-type, given the current tactical situation in WM.

2.2 STM: Dynamic Knowledge Representation

STM is a blackboard-type storage area for the PRM [2]. STM stores data structures that are referenced and manipulated during the plan recognition process. The different components of the model opportunistically read from and write to this area of memory in performing their respective tasks. In the course of the plan recognition process, templates are retrieved from LTM and instantiated in STM with the appropriate multi-agent data based on the values in WM.

3. PLAN RECOGNITION PROCESS

PM employs both top-down and bottom-up processing to formulate multi-agent mission hypotheses regarding the current and future activities of the agents (see Figure 6). A new piece of information received by the system can lead to top-down activation, resulting in the generation of expectations of future activity, or, if the information uniquely describes the behavior of some agent, it can opportunistically trigger bottom-up activation of a plan or an event. These activations are combined to produce hypotheses of the activity of multiple agents under observation.

3.1 Top-Down/Bottom-Up Hypothesis Activation

The top-down component generates expectations of future behavior by first hypothesizing high-level goals, then feasible subgoals to accomplish these goals, and finally missions that could be used to accomplish the subgoals. The hypotheses are created by matching factors which represent our knowledge about non-behavioral aspects of the observed agents and the current situation. The state of tensions, the nationality of the agents, the platform identification of the agents, the number of units, and the geographical location of the scenario all contribute to our expectation of future behavior. We compute a degree of match based upon these factors for each goal node in LTM; if the degree of match is sufficiently high, a template instance of the node is placed in a set of *candidate* (or plausible) top-down generated hypotheses in STM. Once the preconditions of a candidate hypothesis are satisfied, it is considered *current* (or possible), and all child (execution) nodes of that hypothesis are considered. The child nodes are

Figure 6 - Plan Recognition Model Process

placed in the candidate set and processed as above, looking for evidence that would make them current. This top-down process results in a set of plausible multi-agent mission hypotheses.

The bottom-up component of the process is responsible for opportunistically activating hypothesis nodes based upon explicit behavior of the observed agents. The bottom-up component is triggered by the critical indicators for some plan or event. For example, the observation of an attack-type platform with weapons is strong support for an ATTACK-type plan, although high-level indications (via the top-down process) of an ATTACK mission might be absent. The bottom-up component of the process activates nodes in LTM by placing an instance of that node in the set of current plausible hypotheses in STM. This bottom-up activation serves to recognize plans and/or events not expected as a result of top-down activation. Through the use of both the top-down and bottom-up processes, we determine a set of plausible multi-agent missions.

3.2 Structure of the Multi-Agent Hypotheses

The system's explanations for the coordinated activity of the adversary are captured in the multi-agent hypotheses. The many possible combinations of agents, roles, and targets can potentially result in a glut of hypotheses; the matching of situation updates against this large set of expectations can impose a great computational burden on the system. To limit this burden, hypotheses are maintained at a general level until sufficiently detailed evidence is received which allows for finer reasoning. For each possible mission we start with the most general hypothesis, which says that the mission is being performed by some subset (initially unknown) of the set of

adversary agents, whose individual roles have not been determined, and that the mission is directed against some member of the set of potential targets.

As an example of how the system keeps the sources of the explosion distinct, consider how the target (i.e. the observer's ships and land bases) of a multi-agent mission is determined. If we combine the determination of the target with the determination of the single-agent plans for each agent, many hypotheses result, (e.g. $n \times m$ hypotheses for n agents performing a STRIKE on m targets). The solution is to "factor out" the common elements of these related hypotheses, namely the agents' behavior which characterizes the STRIKE, from the potential targets in the target set. This allows us to reason independently about plans and the targets of those plans. Since the determination of the target is very similar for any mission (physical proximity, high degree of approach), we can determine the target of the mission in a plan-independent fashion, bringing to bear agent-independent factors in the context of the situation.

To manage the combinatorial possibilities, a multi-agent hypothesis consists of an agent/role matrix and potential target list. The agent/role matrix allows us to determine which agents in WM best fill the various roles (plans) of the template (see Figure 7). The matrix is populated with a degree of fit of each agent's activity with respect to the various single-agent plans that comprise the template. The degree of fit is computed from the DOM of agent observations against the expected and observable conditions of the plan structures. The potential targets of the agents' mission are stored in an ordered list which reflects the most likely target at any given time based on a number of state variables that relate the agent and the target, including proximity, direction, closure rate, etc.

Figure 7 - Multi-Agent Hypothesis

As the participants in the mission carry out their activities, the target set is dynamically ordered on the basis of the spatial behavior of the observed agents. At the same time, target-independent hypotheses are maintained of the roles that the individual participants will perform. Once enough evidence is gathered, a clearer picture of the target of the mission and the individual roles of the participating agents should emerge. In the ideal case the target set will have a single highly-ranked target and the participants in the mission will have a single role with a high degree of match; this means that the system has produced the most specific hypothesis that it can. However, lack of good data, a novel mission execution, or deception on the part of the adversary may contribute to the system not being able to produce highly specific hypotheses.

3.3 Processing Multi-Agent Hypotheses

Once instantiated, multi-agent hypotheses are compared against updates of agent behavior. The processing that a multi-agent hypothesis undergoes is dictated by the type of situation update that is received. There are three types of situation updates: 1) the introduction of a new agent, 2) the bottom-up activation of a single-agent plan, and 3) updates on the behavior of existing agents. Processing for each update type is described below. When observations sufficiently match expected agent behavior, plans and events are grounded. This is also described below.

Integration of New Agents. When a new agent is reported, an attempt is made to fit the agent into each existing multi-agent hypothesis. This is accomplished by determining the set of possible single-agent plans the new agent can perform in the context of a multi-agent template. The past activity of the existing agents plays a role in keeping the set of possible plans for the new agent to a manageable size. Since we believe that multi-agent missions will be executed in the most efficient manner possible, we remove from our set of expectations those plans which have either already been performed by other agents or will not help the mission to progress. Thus the templates, coupled with a history of past and ongoing plans, allow us to form expectations of which single-agent constitutes the next logical step in the multi-agent mission.

For the system to expect an agent to perform some plan, the plan must be plausible in light of our knowledge of the agent (e.g. his identity, the type of aircraft, how many aircraft, etc.). A plan is plausible if the DOM of the plan's expected/observables conditions, relative to agent observations, surpasses a predefined threshold of expectation. This threshold of expectation can be determined by the user based upon how much expectation he wants the system to produce; low thresholds of expectation will cause the system to

hypothesize larger sets of plans for the agents to perform. If there are roles within a mission template still to be fulfilled, then the new agent is added to the agent set of the multi-agent hypothesis. This will allow us to interpret his future behavior in the context of this hypothesis. If we fail to find a multi-agent hypothesis in progress which can accommodate the new agent, we will create a new multi-agent hypothesis containing the agent which represents the system's belief that the new agent will be the first participant in a new multi-agent mission.

As an example of how a new agent is fit into an existing multi-agent hypothesis, consider a hypothesis for an ATTACK mission. We first determine which plans are temporally imminent; these plans might include TANKING, STRIKE, and FIGHTER ESCORT. Now we must compute the DOM for the Expected Conditions of each of these plans relative to observations on our new agent. For instance, if we know the type of aircraft of the new agent, we can reduce the plan set on the basis of our expectations of which plans will be performed by the agent's aircraft type.

Bottom-Up Activation of Plan Hypotheses. When a single-agent plan is activated bottom-up, the multi-agent templates which can possibly employ this plan are determined. For example, a COUNTER-MEASURES plan is a possible component of the ATTACK mission, but not normally associated with the MONITOR mission. At this point, each of the multi-agent hypotheses which could accommodate the activated plan are visited. If the plan can be fit into the sequence of past plans within the hypothesis, the performing agent of the plan is added to the hypothesis's agent set (if not already under consideration). If there are no existing multi-agent hypotheses that can accommodate the activated plan, then a hypothesis for a mission which requires the plan will be created.

Updating Current Mission and Plan Hypotheses. When updates are received on the behavior of existing agents in a hypothesis's agent set, the hypothesis's target set is reordered with respect to decreasing likelihood of being the target. Target ordering is computed as a function of the distance and degree of approach of each member of the agent set relative to each member of the target set. Next, the DOMs of the conditional attributes of the hypothesis's constituent plans are recalculated with respect to the updated agent behavior. The agent/role matrix entries are updated to reflect the degree of fit resulting from the new DOM values. Finally, the degree of belief in the overall hypothesis is recomputed by taking a weighted average of the DOM's of all constituent plans. The constituent plans which are most critical to the success of the mission, such as a STRIKE plan in the context of an ATTACK mission, contribute the most weight to the overall DOM.

Grounding Plan and Event Hypotheses. At this point each of the multi-agent hypotheses will have been updated to reflect the new information received. When the collected evidence for a component of one of the hypotheses is sufficiently strong, that component is grounded, adding it to the history of plans. The degree of fit between the observed behavior of an agent and the expected observable behavior, stored in LTM, determines what actions have occurred. If the degree of fit surpasses the predefined grounding threshold, then enough evidence has been observed to believe that the action has occurred. The grounding threshold must be kept in mind when LTM is being constructed, since the nodes in LTM must have their impacts adjusted such that a sufficient amount of evidence will allow the threshold to be surpassed. The decision to ground events is made when a current event's degree of match

is surpassed by the degree of match of one of the expected events [2]; if the peak value of the current event is above the grounding threshold, the event may be grounded. A plan is grounded when its critical event is grounded. Multi-agent missions are grounded when a mission-specific critical plan set has been grounded. A goal is grounded when a mission which achieves the goal has been grounded. The hypotheses which have been grounded will be used in generating expectations of future behavior, which are utilized when a new agent is introduced.

Based upon which plans are grounded (i.e. have occurred), which are active (i.e. currently being hypothesized), and which are non-active (i.e. yet to be hypothesized), a vertical slice through the mission template is defined to fix an estimate of the current progress of the mission (see Figure 4). This vertical slice defines an interval of "current activity" within a mission template.

4. STATUS AND FUTURE WORK

The multi-agent PRM has been developed on a Symbolics 3670 and is exercised by a simulation/testbed that supplies moderate fidelity tactical scenarios. The goal/mission/plan hierarchy in LTM has been compiled in the course of knowledge acquisition activities conducted with Naval tactical decision makers.

The data supplied by the testbed to the model's WM is assumed processed by an intelligent data fusion "front-end" and hence all reports on a given agent's activities are assumed correct and correlated. An ATMS-like reason maintenance system has been developed [8] to allow the PRM to reason with the most specific set of observations of an agent's activity. This data set encompasses all observations of a given agent's activity recorded so far. If it is discovered later that an observation is in error (faulty sensor, incorrect reading, etc.) the system reverts to the next most specific set of consistent data. This corresponds to selecting the largest consistent superset of an ATMS lattice environment. Judicious management of this environment to combat the combinatorial explosion of the power set of observations is the subject of further study. Likewise, for each hypothesis maintained, individual merit and competitor killing strategies will be needed to keep the number of hypotheses considered at a manageable level.

Currently, the multiple agents operate synergistically under the same high-level goal structure. In the future, we plan to relax this restriction and consider agents operating within individual goal/mission/plan hierarchies. Where goals overlap, alliances among agents may form and the goal/mission/plan hierarchies merge to yield a centralized structure. Where goals conflict, goal/mission/plan hierarchies remain separate and adversarial interaction ensues. Counterplanning strategies similar to those found in the POLITICS system [4] may then be invoked.

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